

Differences in Mental Health of Doctoral Students Over a One-Year Period in the Autonomous University of Barcelona

Claudia Tejada-Gallardo¹, Anna Muro², Maria Paola Jiménez-Villamizar² and Stefan T. Mol³
1 University of Lleida
2 Autonomous University of Barcelona
3 University of Amsterdam

Purpose

In the context of implementing mental health policies at a local level among universities, the Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB) started working towards a healthier and more sustainable campus in 2018 (Healthy and Sustainable Campus Plan, 2018-2022). The UAB, in collaboration with the Catalan Net of Healthy Universities, works to promote improvements towards a healthier campus. It has implemented several actions that are aimed at promoting mental health and emotional well-being among members of the academic community. Following the guidelines of the European Charter for Researchers (EURAXESS), UAB is working towards a greater understanding of the mental health of members of the researchers' community, especially of Early Career Researchers (ECRs), given their vulnerability to mental health issues as previous reports from other universities have shown. In order to provide a comprehensive understanding of mental health, these efforts are targeted not only at the more conventional negative indicators (i.e., psychopathology or psychological distress) but also incorporates positive indicators (i.e., well-being). Accordingly, the present study aims (1) to explore the positive and negative indicators of doctoral students' mental health in two academic courses (i.e., two different years and cohorts) and (2) extend the research on the understanding of whether or not positive and negative mental health indicators are differentially predicted by individual differences (i.e., gender) and context (i.e., satisfaction with the learning process and relationships with supervisor[s]).

Design

A cross-sequential design (combination of cross-sectional and longitudinal design) was performed in the academic courses of 2021-2022 and 2022-2023. This is two measurement waves with two different cohorts.

Sample

Sample size, mean age, and percentage of females are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. *Sample characteristics*

	Wave 1 (Academic course 21-22)	Wave 2 (Academic course 22-23)	Total
Sample size	176	152	328
Mean age	31,32	32	31,61
% of females	37	63,2	49,1

Instruments

The responses were gathered through an on-line platform using previously validated questionnaires commonly used in the psychological research:

- 1. Positive and Negative Affect Scale (PANAS;** López et al., 2015). The PANAS measures a pattern of experiencing positive emotions relating to emotional well-being and the experience of negative emotions relating to emotional discomfort. It includes two subscales (i.e., positive and negative) assessed using a total of 20 items, 10 items each, and has a Likert-type response from 1 to 5.
- 2. General Anxiety Disorder-2 (GAD-2;** García et al., 2012). The GAD-2 briefly measures the presence of symptoms associated with generalized anxiety disorder. The scale consists of 2 items on a Likert-type response scale from 0 to 3 and is used to assess the presence of symptoms in the previous two weeks. The final score can range from 0 to 6 and can be used to assign a provisional diagnosis: no anxiety disorder (0–2) and probable anxiety disorder (3–6).
- 3. Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9;** Kroenke et al., 2001). The PHQ-9 items follow the nine criteria specified in the DSM-IV diagnostic manual for screening for depressive disorder. It includes 9 items in a Likert-type response scale from 0 to 3 and is used to assess the presence of symptoms in the previous two weeks. The total scale score is 27, and scores of 10–14 points, 15–19 points, and 20–27 points indicate moderate, moderately severe, and severe levels of depressive symptoms, respectively.

Statistical Analyses

A multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was employed to verify differences in mental health of doctoral students in two academic courses. Mental health scales were used as

dependent variables and gender and time of measurement were used as independent variables. Finally, a linear regression model was employed to observe how (1) the satisfaction with the learning process and (2) the relationships with the supervisor(s) predicted mental health indicators. These analyses were performed using SPSS version 27.

Results

Preliminary results showed that all mental health indicators means did not differ significantly from Wave 1 to Wave 2. Specifically, the total sample presented mild depression symptoms, a score of 9.4 close to diagnosis of moderate depression symptoms (scores of 10 or above). Regarding gender, the only significant variable that differed between males and females was anxiety, being higher for males (score of 3) and indicating presence of anxiety disorder.

Regression models (including positive and negative indicators of mental health) for the course 21-22 showed that lower negative affect was significantly predicted by satisfaction with the learning process ($\beta = -.260, p = .006$) and a good relationship with the supervisor(s) ($\beta = -.296, p = .011$). Regression model for the course 22-23 showed that being satisfied with the learning process significantly predicted positive affect ($\beta = .369, p < .001$) and lower negative affect ($\beta = -.207, p = .044$). Also, having a good relationship with the supervisor(s) significantly predicted positive affect ($\beta = .326, p = .002$), lower negative affect ($\beta = -.468, p < .001$), and lower depression symptoms ($\beta = -.046, p = .024$).

Implications

The findings based on the data of two academic courses suggest that mental health indicators are relatively stable among doctoral students over a one-year period, however, negative indicators show a likely trend of depression and anxiety cases in doctoral students. These data are supported by previous research indicating that the estimated incidence of mental problems in doctoral students is 2.84 times higher than that observed in the generally highly educated population before the COVID-19 and increased dramatically during and after the pandemic around the world (Kismihók et al., 2022; Lau & Petrorius, 2019; Levecque et al., 2017; Sorrel et al., 2020). Also, it is important to remark that the degree of satisfaction with the learning process of doctoral students and the relationship that they have with their supervisor(s) are potential antecedents of mental health, especially of positive and negative affect and depression. All these results support the necessary investments in well-being promotion among educational settings since it would benefit public health services as a preventive strategy that could reduce

the need for clinical assistance in mental health. Accordingly, further research on effective mental health training is highly encouraged to assess and analyze their impact on doctoral students' mental health and to continue advancing towards more sustainable and healthier research environments in doctoral communities, as a priority of the European Research Area (Kismihók et al., 2022; Lau & Petrorius, 2019; O'Neill & Schroijen, 2018).

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